

Phenotypic Variability and Growth Performance of Three Nigerian Chickens Reared in South-East Nigeria

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Abstract

An investigation into the growth performance of three Nigerian chickens was carried out. One hundred and fifty (150) day old chicks were used for this purpose comprising fifty (50) birds each of the Noiler, Naked neck and the Normal feather chickens in a Completely Randomized Experimental Design. The birds were raised on deep litter from day old to sixteenth week of age during which data were collected on the body weight, linear body measurement and the performance index. Data collected were subjected to one-way analysis of variance using SPSS software package. Results obtained showed significant differences ($P < 0.05$) on the performance index and all linear body parameters measured. The Naked neck showed a better feed conversion ratio (2.11 ± 0.088) compared to the other breeds. Noiler recorded the best performance in all the measured traits. The better performance of Noiler over the other two breeds could be attributed to its genetic make-up, which could be linked to the development of the breed.

Keywords: Phenotype, Linear morphometry, Noiler, Normal feather, Naked neck

INTRODUCTION

Poultry sub-sector creates employment and promotes overall economic development (King' Ori *et al.*, 2010), while local chicken production contributes to the income and general wellbeing of the rural dwellers (Sonaiya, 2007). Chicken meat production has proven to be the most prevalent alternative towards reducing the incidence of animal protein deficiency in human diets (Obasoyo *et al.*, 2005). The low animal protein consumption in Nigeria highlights the need for improvement in livestock production as a panacea to protein insufficiency in human nutrition.

Growth performance of an animal is a phenotypic expression, which is the outward expression of the animal genetic make-up (Ojedapo *et al.*, 2012). Growth in animals involves increase in body size and changes in functional capabilities of the various tissues and organs of the body (Akpan *et*

al., 2022). Recent studies have shown that other growth traits such as body length, shank length and breast girth can serve as good indicators of growth other than body weight (Ige, 2013). Many of the features related to the functions of chickens have been substantially improved by the genetic selection through crossing the different varieties to meet the increasing global need for chicken meat (Rekaya *et al.*, 2013). Hence the need to determine the linear morphometry and growth performance as indicators of best performing breed of three Nigerian chickens.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study location: The study was conducted at the Poultry Unit of Teaching and Research Farms, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo Ohaji-Egbema, Imo State. Ohaji Egbema is situated in the humid tropics at latitude 5^o15'N and longitude 6^o58'E with a total mean annual rainfall of about 2500mm and average temperature of 26–30°C (NIMET, 2014).

Management of experimental birds: One hundred and fifty birds were used comprising 50 Noiler, 50 Naked neck and 50 Normal feather chickens. The birds were raised from day old to sixteen weeks of age during which data were collected. The birds were brooded and raised on a deep litter pens. Feed and water were provided *ad libitum* throughout the experiment. Daily management operations such as washing of the feeders and drinkers were carried out daily and litters were changed as at when due. Vaccination and medication schedule were strictly adhered to and bio-safety was also ensured.

Experimental design and statistical model: The birds were housed on three deep litter pens according to their breed. The experimental design used was Completely Randomized (CRD), thus the model:

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + \beta_i + \sum ij$$

Where:

Y_{ij} = Observation on the j th individual bird of the i th breed

μ = the overall mean

β_i = breed effect

$\sum ij$ = Random residual effect

Data Collection

Body weight (g): The birds were weighed individually at the beginning of the experiment and subsequently every week throughout the study using electronic digital scale.

Feed Intake (g): Amount of feed consumed determined by subtracting the quantity left over the next morning from the quantity offered.

Average weight gain: This was calculated as:

$$\text{Weight gain} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{\text{NoD}}$$

Where

W_1 = Initial weight

W_2 = Final weight

NoD = Number of days

Feed conversion ratio: $\frac{\text{Feed Intake}}{\text{Weight gain}}$

Linear morphometry

Body Length (cm): The distance between the last cervical vertebra and the caudal vertebra was taken as the body length.

Breast girth (cm): This was taken as the circumference of the chest around the deepest region.

Shank length (cm): It was taken as the length of the tarso-metatarsus from the anterior end joining the tibia bone to the first digit.

Drumstick length (cm): This was measured as the distance between the patella and the posterior end of the tibia joining the tarso metatarsus.

Drumstick girth: This was taken as the circumference at the biggest region of the drumstick.

Height at withers (cm): This was measured on the dorsal midline at the highest point on the withers.

Shoulder to tail length: This was taken as the distance from the point of the shoulder to pin bone or to the end of occygeal vertebrate.

Wing length (cm): The length of the wing from the end of the wing to the bone that attaches the wing to the body.

Data collected were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the General Linear Model procedure of SPSS (2019). Means were separated using the Duncan Multiple Range Test of the software package.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the growth performance index of the Noiler, Naked neck and Normal feather. The result is presented in form of means from general linear model for initial and final body weights respectively, weight gains, initial feed intake and final feed intake, average feed intake, daily feed intake and feed conversion ratio. Noiler recorded significant ($P < 0.05$) higher initial body weight (0.035 ± 0.00) than the other two breeds (0.0312 ± 0.00) and (0.0299 ± 0.00) for Naked neck and Normal feather respectively. Non-significant difference ($P > 0.05$) was observed in the final body weight and weight gain of the three breeds. Non-significant ($P > 0.05$) difference was observed in the initial feed intake between the Noiler and the naked neck while significant difference was observed in the final feed intake, mean feed intake and daily feed intake amongst the three breeds of chicken. Significant ($P < 0.05$) feed conversion ratio was recorded between the naked neck (2.11 ± 0.088) and the other two breeds (3.30 ± 0.166) (3.06 ± 0.156) Noiler and Normal feather respectively. The result showed that the Naked neck has better feed conversion ratio (2.11 ± 0.088) than the other two breed. This is followed by Normal feather chicken with feed conversion ratio of 3.06 ± 0.156 . Ajayi (2010) reported that Naked neck genes confer better feed conversion, growth rate and feed efficiency compared to the normal feathered chicken. The naked neck gene (Na) and its effect on heat dissipation positively increases feed intake resulting in higher body weight under high temperatures (Islam and Nishibori, 2009). N'Dri *et al.* (2006) reported the feed conversion ratio of 3.15 in slow growing line of chicken which is close to the values obtained in this study.

Table 1: Growth performance index of the three Nigerian chicken breeds

Performance index	Noiler	Naked neck	Normal feather
Initial body weight (kg)	0.035 ± 0.00^a	0.0312 ± 0.00^b	0.0299 ± 0.00^b
Final body weight (kg)	2.02 ± 0.105	1.99 ± 0.065	1.72 ± 0.082

Weight gain (kg)	1.99 ± 0.105	1.96 ± 0.065	1.69 ± 0.082
Initial feed intake (kg)	0.71 ± 0.000 ^a	0.67 ± 0.000 ^a	0.58 ± 0.000 ^b
Final feed intake (kg)	6.07 ± 0.028 ^a	3.99 ± 0.055 ^c	4.84 ± 0.061 ^b
Mean feed intake (kg)	5.24 ± 0.020 ^a	3.21 ± 0.062 ^c	4.23 ± 0.075 ^b
Daily feed intake (kg)	0.05 ± 0.000 ^a	0.03 ± 0.001 ^c	0.04 ± 0.001 ^b
Feed conversion ratio (FCR)	3.30 ± 0.166 ^a	2.11 ± 0.088 ^b	3.06 ± 0.156 ^a

Means within rows with different superscripts are significantly difference (P<0.05)

Table 2 presents results on linear morphometry in the three Nigerian breeds of chicken, significant difference ($P<0.05$) was observed in all the parameters measured (body weight, body length, breast girth, shank length, drumstick length and girth, shoulder to tail length, height at withers and wing length). Noiler recorded the best performance in all the measured traits similarly, followed by the Naked neck breed which outperformed the normal feather in all the measured traits. The better performance of Noiler over the other two breeds could be attributed to its genetic make-up which could be linked to the development of the breed, since Noiler is a cross between broilers and cockerels. Yakubu *et al.* (2008) reported that naked neck birds perform better in terms of body weight than normal feathered birds. The Naked neck gene (Na) was reported to increase breast yield meat while its advantage over normal feathered conditions were found to be exhibited during egg production (Adebambo, 2015). Okafor (2019) reported the body length range of 23.00 ± 0.31 to 26.31 ± 0.38 cm, shank length of 10.12 to 11.94cm, and breast girth range of 21.46 to 27.15cm.

Table 2: Linear morphometry of the three Nigerian breeds of chicken

Linear measurement	Noiler	Naked neck	Normal feather
Body weight (kg)	1.150 ± 0.020 ^a	1.039 ± 0.020 ^b	0.909 ± 0.020 ^c
Body length (cm)	33.37 ± 0.127 ^a	32.16 ± 0.127 ^b	31.46 ± 0.127 ^c
Breast length (cm)	21.66 ± 0.119 ^a	20.95 ± 0.119 ^b	19.78 ± 0.117 ^c
Shank length (cm)	10.03 ± 0.053 ^a	9.77 ± 0.058 ^b	9.43 ± 0.058 ^c
Drumstick length (cm)	12.99 ± 0.131 ^a	12.34 ± 0.131 ^b	12.09 ± 0.131 ^c
Drumstick girth (cm)	9.76 ± 0.084 ^a	9.52 ± 0.034 ^b	9.14 ± 0.084 ^c
Shoulder to tail length (cm)	17.53 ± 0.085 ^a	17.00 ± 0.085 ^b	16.76 ± 0.085 ^c
Height at withers (cm)	22.29 ± 0.095 ^a	21.97 ± 0.095 ^b	20.50 ± 0.095 ^c
Wing length	18.47 ± 0.078 ^a	17.92 ± 0.078 ^b	17.67 ± 0.078 ^c

abc Means within rows with different superscripts are significantly difference (P>0.05)

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that although Noiler chicken showed poor feed conversion ratio, it showed the best performance compared to the other breeds which could be attributed to the development of the breed.

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